

“Think out of the box”: Opportunities from COVID-19 for libraries

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Abstract

Crises often spur societies to rethink their structures to meet immediate needs and to prepare for the future. While the COVID-19 pandemic led public libraries to rethink how they serve their communities, there is sparse literature exploring how opportunities from the pandemic can be leveraged. This paper examines such opportunities from the COVID-19 pandemic as described by African public librarians. We conducted virtual interviews with 11 head librarians in nine African countries and analyzed the data using inductive thematic analysis. We found that many librarians improved their digital skills. Some libraries that hitherto did not have computers and Internet connectivity were provided with such digital tools. Also, most of the librarians leveraged low-cost digital platforms like WhatsApp to share information. We use their experiences to think about how public librarians can leverage opportunities from the pandemic to meet the information needs of their communities.

Keywords: Public libraries, Africa, Asset-Based Approach, WhatsApp, COVID-19

Introduction

Crises are bound to happen in human lives. While we cannot predict most of these crises, we can mitigate these unforeseen situations by taking immediate steps to overcome the situation and thinking about possible futures, opportunities, and creating action plans (Hines and Bishop, 2015; Van Der Laan, 2021). Public institutions have a key role in helping their communities prepare and respond effectively to emergent and unforeseen crises (Phillips, Neal and Webb, 2016; Tyler and Sadiq, 2018). When COVID-19 struck, the goal of public institutions at the peak of the pandemic was to keep people safe and to continue offering services as best possible.

As access points to information, libraries, especially public and community libraries, played significant roles (both information and non-information related roles) during the pandemic to meet the urgent needs of their communities (Bugre, Jowaisas and Young, 2023; Chase, 2021; Chigwada, 2021; Guo et al., 2022; Robert et al., 2021). For instance, some small and rural public libraries from developed places like the United States (US) collaborated with other departments to serve as childcare facilities for essential workers during the pandemic (Chase, 2021). Some public libraries in Africa during the pandemic also scanned and shared

learning materials with students using WhatsApp – a multimedia messaging application software – to support the students’ preparation towards their terminal examinations (Bugre, Jowaisas and Young, 2023).

However, for most public and community libraries in Africa, the virtual transition was either impossible or difficult. This is because, first, most public and community libraries in Africa are low-resourced (Elbert, Fuegi and Lipeikaite, 2012) to provide digital information services. Second, many communities in Africa have no or low Internet connection, or are not even connected to electricity (Joel and Camble, 2021; Kardefelt-Winther et al., 2022; Majola and Mudau, 2022). So, people cannot access virtual services seamlessly. Similarly, the illiteracy rate among all adults (over 15-year-old) in Africa is on average about 25.96% as compared to 7.62% of the rest of the world regions (Galan, 2025). This means Africa has a high adult population of people who cannot read in any language which can affect their ability to browse virtual information services.

Given the above challenges, one wonders how public and community libraries in Africa managed to meet the information needs of their community members during the COVID-19 pandemic. What did they learn from these challenges, and what opportunities from the pandemic can they seize to continue to support their community members with their information needs now and during possible future crises? Such insights will be relevant to low-resourced libraries and contribute to Library and Information Science (LIS) literature on library information services arising from the COVID-19 pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic also provides an important case study in understanding how libraries can utilize their existing resources to address information needs during crises. To this end, we investigate the following research questions:

RQ1: What were the opportunities from the COVID-19 pandemic for public and community libraries in Africa?

RQ2: Which of the opportunities can they seize to continue to serve their communities now and in future crises?

We answer RQ1 through interviews we conducted with head librarians in 9 African countries, purposively sampled across the 5 subregions of Africa- Northern, Southern, Western, Eastern and Central Africa (African Union, n.d.). Based on inductive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006, 2021) of the interviews, we answer RQ2 by proposing recommendations, which suggest

that libraries could focus on their existing strengths to meet the information needs of their communities. The recommendations are framed through the Asset-Based Community Development model-ABCD (Kretzmann and McKnight, 1993; Russell and McKnight, 2022; Williment, 2009).

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: a) a brief literature review related to public and community libraries management of the COVID-19 pandemic globally; and the Asset-Based Community Development model; b) the research methods detailing how the research was conducted; c) presentation and discussion of findings which examines how low-resourced libraries can strategically leverage opportunities arising from their pandemic experiences to serve the information needs of the communities now and during future crises; and d) a conclusion which proposes a research agenda to further explore how libraries can use the asset-based approach in solving challenges that they encounter.

Literature review

Public and community libraries innovative services during the COVID-19 pandemic

Following the declaration of COVID-19 as a pandemic and the subsequent stay-at-home orders announced in most countries, the operations and service delivery of many public and community libraries around the world became very challenging (Alajmi and Albudaiwi, 2021; Freudenberger, 2020; Smith, 2020; Wang and Lund, 2020). But when the initial stay-at-home orders were eased, some public libraries around the world found very innovative ways to support their patrons to navigate the pandemic. For instance, some libraries in China set up book corners in isolation centers for COVID patients (Guo et al., 2022; Kou et al., 2021; Xin, 2022). Other public libraries in the US and elsewhere organized online yoga, virtual live musical concerts and made their Wi-Fi accessible outside the library building for patrons (Chase, 2021; Freudenberger, 2020; Goddard, 2020; Goek, 2021; Lenstra and D' Arpa, 2022; Syn, Sinn and Kim, 2023; Wilson, 2021). In the U.S., public libraries adapted their regular services using social media platforms like Facebook Live to host virtual events, bookmobiles to deliver Wi-Fi access, and their spaces as vaccination clinics (Syn, Sinn and Kim, 2023). Rural and low-resourced libraries utilized outdoor areas to host programs such as walking exercises, painting, and agricultural activities to support their communities while following public health guidelines (Lenstra and D' Arpa, 2022). Examples from other countries including Canada (Dalmer and Griffin, 2022;

Intahchomphoo and Vellino, 2024; Roberts and Clarke, 2024; Rosale, 2021), Portugal (Alvim, Silva and Borges, 2020), Serbia (Pesic and Tanasijevic, 2022), Indonesia (Srirahayu, Harisanty and Anugrah, 2023) and Australia (Smith, 2020; Wakeling et al., 2021) showcase a variety of similar adapted services undertaken by public libraries. For instance, some public libraries in Toronto allowed their spaces to be used as community food banks and assigned library staff members to make care calls to vulnerable community members to address social isolation (Roberts and Clarke, 2024). Generally, COVID-19 highlighted existing global disparities in library resources but also sparked innovative solutions regardless of resources available such as addressing digital divides and helping people navigate the pandemic.

There are fewer studies on innovative public and community library services related to the pandemic in developing countries. Systematic reviews of libraries initiatives during COVID-19 focus largely on academic libraries or rarely mention public libraries from developing countries (Ayeni, Agbaje and Tippler, 2021; Kostagiolas and Katsani, 2021). Limited studies from countries such as Sri Lanka (Dilrukshi, Illangarathne and Wanasinghe, 2021), Indonesia (Srirahayu, Harisanty and Anugrah, 2023), and Serbia (Pesic and Tanasijevic, 2022) show that, while resources were limited, libraries also tried to use the resources already available to them to serve their communities during the pandemic. In the Indonesian example, public librarians initiated innovative reading tours. The librarians went to schools to bring students to the library when the COVID-19 stay-at-home protocols were relaxed (Srirahayu, Harisanty and Anugrah, 2023). In Serbia, a librarian delivered library materials to elderly inhabitants of a village by bicycle including delivery of medicines to meet urgent health needs of the elderly (Pesic and Tanasijevic, 2022).

Likewise, across Africa, for libraries that did not have the means (Shonhe, 2022) to provide similar services like their counterparts in developed countries, the pandemic encouraged other forms of innovation such as empathetic services to assist patrons in ways not traditionally associated with African public libraries such as meal services and sharing scanned library materials with patrons through WhatsApp (Bugre, Jowaisas and Young, 2023; Chigwada, 2021; Chisita and Ngulube, 2022; Joel and Camble, 2021; Shonhe, 2022). Other community libraries delivered books to rural areas by local means, such as using camels in Ethiopia (Save the Children, 2020). In a nutshell, the above initiatives were not only crucial in addressing the needs

of their communities during the pandemic, but the initiatives were largely based on resources that the libraries already had at their disposal.

On the contrary, some public and community libraries in Africa could not provide any support to community members based on challenges such as lack of digital technologies, Internet connection, electricity issues, high cost of Internet data, and little or poor digital skills of staff and community people (African Library and Information Association and Institutions [AfLIA], 2020; Chigwada, 2021; Otike et al., 2021; Shonhe, 2022). Digital skills refer to the ability to use digital devices and networks to create, share and find information (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2023). Perhaps, because of the worldwide transition to digital solutions during the stay-at-home orders period of the COVID-19 pandemic, some librarians thought that the only way they could support patrons during the pandemic was limited to digital service. This perception illustrates the understandable challenge for libraries who did not have tools to facilitate virtual dissemination of information during the COVID-19 stay-at-home orders. But it also suggests a possible deficit mindset of many libraries who even after the end of the stay-at-home orders still felt they could not provide any information services to their communities without virtual tools.

There are many examples of libraries as illustrated above that initiated services during the pandemic that were not digital solutions. For instance, some libraries in China specially chose books for hospital patients and staff to ease panic and promote mental health (Xin, 2022). Indonesian librarians accompanied children from school to public libraries to encourage reading after the lockdown (Srirahayu, Harisanty and Anugrah, 2023). These examples highlight the unique opportunities available to libraries to assist their communities in times of crisis with or without virtual tools using resources at their disposal.

Therefore, we ask: how can librarians leverage their experiences from the pandemic to assist their communities now and in possible crises? Given that many African libraries are low-resourced (Elbert, Fuegi and Lipeikaite, 2012), we examine in the next section an asset-based approach- the Asset-Based Community Development (ABCD) model. This model provides insights into how institutions can capitalize on their existing resources and strengths to serve the needs of their clients. We start by looking briefly at what a community-led public library approach entails to demonstrate the importance of running library services that meet the needs of the community. Then we focus on the ABCD model and how it can assist low-resourced

libraries. Given that, as noted above, some libraries demonstrated how they can mobilize their existing resources to support their communities during the pandemic, the following review provides theoretical background to RQ2 which looks at the opportunities from the COVID-19 pandemic that public and community libraries can seize to continue to serve their communities now and even in future crises.

Conceptual framework

Community-led public libraries approach

A community-led public library approach is the idea that everyone in the community should be able to access their information needs at the library and influence the services that the library provides, and its future direction (Hussey, 2021). A community-led public library approach revolves around the idea of not offering services just based on what librarians think patrons may need but what the community members or patrons actually need (Pateman and Williment, 2016). This involves working with the community members to identify and satisfy their information needs and not merely in the community (Campbell, 2005).

Nonetheless, libraries cannot afford what they do not have. Therefore, a community-led library service especially for less-resourced libraries should focus on existing resources that they have at their disposal and how to use those resources to implement information services needed by their communities. This type of community-led service delivery which focuses on an entity's existing resources as well as the collective efforts of the community members in creating and running the service is referred to as the Asset-Based Community Development (ABCD) model (Kretzmann and McKnight, 1993; Russell and McKnight, 2022). Using this approach to deliver services and to engage community members offers promise for less resourced libraries to capitalize on whatever existing resources they have at their disposal to serve their communities.

Asset-Based Community Development model

The Asset-Based Community Development model is an approach that assesses an institution's strengths and resources to solve problems. The ABCD approach was pioneered by John P. Kretzmann and John L. McKnight (Edwards et al., 2013). Both Kretzmann and McKnight are Urban Studies scholars and community development experts. The ABCD model is as a result of the lessons they learned by studying successful community activities led by low-resourced

organizations in many impoverished communities across the United States (Kretzmann and McKnight, 1993). The ABCD model focuses on the belief that an institution and the community where it is situated have the gifts, talents, resources and strength of individuals or groups to solve its problems and initiate solutions (Kretzmann and McKnight, 1993; McKnight and Russell, 2018). It minimizes the expectations that the only way to solve the problems is to have more resources from others. It involves asking questions such as: what resources and abilities do we have in the institution or/and community right now to address this problem ourselves? (Kretzmann and McKnight, 1993).

This model has been applied successfully by some public libraries in sustainable development and community engagement initiatives (Hapel, 2020). For instance, Hapel (2020) points out that the Dokk1 Aarhus Library—a world class library in Denmark— is based on the ABCD model. For instance, during the planning stage, the architects and the planning board focused on the expertise and experiences of both the library and their community members. Community members including elementary school kids were involved in the planning and the design of the library building as co-creators. Similarly, even before the Dokk1 Aarhus Library, Hapel recalls how he successfully employed this ABCD model to provide services for immigrants and refugees in North Jutland. He said he focused on resources such as the expertise, talents, experiences and passions among library staff and the immigrants/refugees. He was interested in what could support the delivery of the library service rather than what the library did not have or perceived deficiencies of the immigrants and the refugees. This is captured in the following lines:

In my early experiences with collaborative library work with immigrants and refugees in North Jutland, we were always looking for assets in the community that could help us create high-quality and relevant programs and services, and it was amazing to see how resourceful people could be. Even those without monetary means or formal education could contribute significantly if the framing was right (Hapel, 2020: 406)

The above testimony demonstrates the promise of ABCD in libraries. Hapel focused on the resources available within the library and the community such as the voluntary time and expertise of refugees and how those resources can support him in resolving the issue at hand.

The ABCD model, first and foremost, invites institutions such as libraries to look at the current skills, talents and experiences of library staff and ask each individual staff member: what

can they do with what they currently have to run a library service, utilizing assets of individuals such as gifts, expertise and experience? Second, it invites libraries to look at the local associations of each library staff member like churches, youth groups, football clubs and ask how the library can collaborate with those local associations so that they both can support each other in developing the community (assets of local associations within the community). Third, it invites libraries to see how they can collaborate with and ensure that services and resources from institutions of government, local businesses and international organizations meet the needs of the library or their community (assets from government institutions, businesses and international organizations within the community). Fourth, it invites libraries to examine how they can take advantage of their own physical assets like their building, land, furniture, computers, books to serve the needs of their community members. Finally, it also invites libraries to examine how to leverage resources outside the community to support locally driven development (Kretzmann and McKnight, 1993; McKnight and Russell, 2018; Russell and McKnight, 2022).

The ABCD model underscores that it is only when institutions help to solve the needs of their communities that the communities in turn will invest their resources to support the institution so that both the community and the institution can prosper. Nonetheless, Kretzmann and McKnight (1993) also stressed that even though the ABCD model focuses on local assets, it does not mean that institutions do not need additional or external support. The ABCD, in fact, rather helps the institution to fully mobilize resources within the institution and to identify accurately the additional/external resources required through partnerships and collaborations. However, despite the huge potential benefits of the ABCD model for libraries, there is sparse literature on its application within African public and community libraries. Secondly, though there is some literature on African libraries related to the COVID-19 pandemic that shows that many of them used social messaging applications like WhatsApp to engage patrons and to deliver information (Bugre, Jowaisas and Young, 2023; Chigwada, 2021), there is little to no literature on how African libraries intend to leverage these opportunities to engage and serve their community members now and in future crises. This paper examines the experiences of African public and community libraries during the COVID-19 and opportunities that they can leverage to serve their community members.

Methods

The researchers conducted virtual interviews (De Villiers et al., 2022) with African librarians to address the research questions for this study which focused on opportunities from the COVID-19 pandemic for public and community libraries.

Recruitment and procedure

We conducted one-on-one semi-structured interviews (Adams, 2015) with 11 heads of public and community libraries across the five subregions of Africa. The interviews were conducted online using Zoom (Oliffe et al., 2021) from March to April 2023. Each interview lasted on average 60 minutes. Semi-structured interviews were appropriate because it allowed each participant to respond in an open-ended fashion based on their particular experience and also allowed the researchers to probe for further depth and clarifications which contributed to the richness of the data (Adams, 2015; Rubin and Rubin, 2011). We purposively sent 28 emails to potential participants who can speak English language from a mailing list of African librarians that we have worked with in the past. Potential participants were also identified through snowballing (recommendations from research participants). Purposive sampling (Campbell et al., 2020) was relevant for this study because we were targeting library heads who were responsible for the day-to-day functioning of a library and who had additional administrative responsibilities over other libraries. We wanted these head librarians to narrate not only their direct or individual experiences but also the experiences of those other libraries. The snowballing (Sadler et al., 2010) helped us to reach participants from subregions where we did not have any prior contacts or subregions where those we initially emailed did not respond. See Figure 1 below on statistics about our call for participation.

Figure 1. Number of emails sent, replies, referrals and participants interviewed

Figure 1 shows the emails we sent to each subregion, the replies and referrals we had as well as the interviews we conducted in each region. As shown from the chart, we sent fewer emails to Northern Africa and Central Africa because those regions are not predominantly English-speaking countries, and we only had one or two contacts from those regions who could communicate in English. We interviewed at least two participants from each subregion except in Central Africa where we had only one participant.

Figure 2 below shows the specific countries where we interviewed librarians. We interviewed heads of libraries from Sierra Leone, Ghana, Nigeria, Egypt, Democratic Republic of Congo, Uganda, Kenya, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

Figure 2. Locations of heads of libraries interviewed

While the data is not fully representative of all libraries across Africa, we tried to sample different funding models of libraries to get a deeper sense of individual experiences so that the insights gained can be transferable (Guba, 1981; Tobin and Begley, 2004) to other contexts or settings. Six of the librarians are from regional/county-level libraries that are heavily dependent on central government funding and donors for books/learning materials. For the other five libraries, one has multiple sources of fundings such as county, central government and companies in their locality. Two of the libraries have partnerships with the United States of America (USA), Danish and German international organizations. The remaining two public libraries are quite unique. They have strong centralized national public library authorities that coordinate funding from the government and other sources. Thus, while these libraries themselves are not representative of the diversity among these institutions across the continent, they represent a purposeful variety in terms of funding models and governance systems.

Similarly, in terms of the credibility and dependability of our findings (Guba, 1981; Tobin and Begley, 2004), we sought participants who could serve as key informants in their contexts. Four of the participants interviewed were heads of the community and public libraries associations in their provinces and the rest of the participants were either regional or provincial head librarians who oversee all public libraries within their province or region. For instance, one of the participants was the head librarian for the second largest province in their country. Thus, though the study relies on the experiences of individual librarians, the librarians we interviewed have oversight responsibilities on other libraries/librarians which we believe increases the credibility and dependability of our findings because the sources have a broad, expansive view of library initiatives in their contexts as well as extensive practical knowledge in the LIS field. We also shared the audio recording transcripts with participants as a means of member checking to increase credibility of their responses (Birt et al., 2016).

Interview instrument

The interview instrument was reviewed by eight Master of Library and Information Science (MLIS) students, two senior information science research scientists, two MLIS instructors and piloted with two librarians. The interview guide sought to ask librarians questions related to their experiences and opportunities from the COVID-19 pandemic such as: Has their libraries changed the way they operate since the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic? What tasks/services were the libraries able to do when their libraries were closed or restricted to the public due to the pandemic? What were the tasks/services they started which they were not previously doing prior to the pandemic? What challenges did they face? What have their libraries or librarians themselves gained from the pandemic? What opportunities can they derive from the pandemic? The above questions were meant as a guide and the researchers asked follow-up questions based on the direction of the conversation.

Data analysis

All the interviews were recorded with participants' permission, transcribed using Otter.ai, cleaned manually and coded using Atlas.ti. After cleaning the transcripts, we sent them to the participants to ask whether there was anything that was not captured or they did not feel comfortable to be cited (Birt et al., 2016). The transcripts were then coded and analyzed using an

inductive thematic analysis approach (Braun and Clarke, 2006, 2021). We identified and interpreted patterns and interesting insights across the datasets (Braun and Clarke, 2006). We employed the inductive approach to ensure that the codes and themes reflected the accounts of the participants from the interview data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The analytic approach was situated within an interpretive constructionist framework (Berger and Luckmann, 2016; Rubin and Rubin, 2011) which allowed us to examine the COVID-19 pandemic experiences of the librarians to identify opportunities for library services and other similar crises in the future. This approach was appropriate because as indicated by Rubin and Rubin (2011), the interpretive constructionist approach allows researchers to elicit the views of participants about their world, work and events they have experienced or observed (Rubin and Rubin, 2011). Rubin and Rubin (2011) explain further that often, participants' views are expressed and interpreted based on their society, professional, political or cultural assumptions. Nonetheless, the interpretive constructionist approach also recognizes the role of researchers in influencing the interpretation of the data and directing the research. However, we tried to interpret the data within the context of the participants based on our experiential knowledge of Africa. The primary researcher has worked as a librarian in Ghana and the other three researchers have also visited different African countries for various library projects.

Braun and Clarke (2006, 2021) outline a six-step thematic analysis process that includes 1) familiarizing oneself with the data and taking notes; 2) systematically coding the data; 3) generating initial themes from the coded and collated data; 4) developing and reviewing themes; 5) refining, defining and naming themes; and 6) producing the report. First, we read the transcripts while listening to the recorded audio files to familiarize ourselves with the data and to correct portions that were not well transcribed. We wrote short notes and took note of potential codes during this step. Second, the first author read each transcript more closely, highlighting and labeling interesting ideas and patterns related to the research questions with short phrases or keywords. Third, the rest of the research team then met to discuss the codes generated and identified some initial themes such as opportunities, fortunes/gains, initiatives, challenges and needs. Fourth, these initial themes were then further reviewed and summarized into two categories in relation to our research questions: 1) opportunities from the pandemic; and 2) lessons from the pandemic. Fifth, we searched among the codes under each theme to identify the

relevant participant quotes that can best articulate these themes. Finally, we then defined each theme and considered the relationship between the themes for the writing of the findings.

We report the findings of the interviews without individual or institutional identifiers to protect the interviewees' privacy. Moreover, the main goal of this study is to highlight the opportunities for public and community libraries following the emergence of the pandemic and not to report on specific libraries or countries. We simply refer to the interviewees by identifiers that we randomly assigned to the transcripts such as "participant 1, 2, 3" and so on. Some quotes have been revised for clarity and to preserve anonymity. The modified portions are enclosed in square brackets [].

Findings

Based on our analysis of the interviews conducted, we identified that the impact of the pandemic on libraries was initially negative but later created some opportunities and spurred evolution of services which suggest potential for community-based services now and in the future. These opportunities include improved digital skills among staff, increased access to IT equipment, and the initiation of new library services. We present our findings with illustrative examples as follows:

Improved digital skills of library staff: - "COVID forced some of us to learn the computer"

We found that despite the challenges that the libraries faced from the onset such as little or poor digital skills of library staff - which mirror those cited above in previous studies (AFLIA, 2020; Joel and Camble, 2021; Chigwada, 2021; Otike et al, 2021; Shonhe, 2022) - many of the librarians improved their digital skills. Digital skills such as teleconferencing application skills and office application to work virtually became a necessity during the COVID-19 pandemic. Unfortunately, from our interviews, many African public and community library staff did not initially have these required digital skills to navigate virtual services. So, during the peak and stay-at-home days of the pandemic, most of the librarians took advantage of that period to upgrade themselves by enrolling in online Office application courses. They also attended online training workshops related to media literacy and misinformation. Many of these online tutorials were facilitated by their country library boards in collaboration with some online

education providers such as Commonwealth of Learning (CoL), Coursera, Udemy and so on. For instance, Participant 1 revealed that he “learnt how to use Zoom, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams and other free online courses”. Similarly, Participant 2 told us that the pandemic gave them “...the opportunity to distinguish between fake and real news” from a workshop. Participant 4 confessed that the pandemic pushed (“forced”) librarians to improve their digital skills. The rest of the participants expressed similar experiences which demonstrate that the pandemic gave public and community librarians in Africa ample time, motivation and access to online learning platforms to pursue digital skills related courses.

The above digital skills have not only benefited the individual librarians, but also their libraries. For instance, the librarians indicated that the skills they learnt and their exposure to virtual interaction software have saved them some expenses because most of their libraries have now adopted virtual meetings. One participant from an Eastern African country with a vibrant national library authority revealed this as follows:

...Before the pandemic, we used to go [to the headquarters] for physical meetings. So, [due to] the pandemic, the meetings were [held] online. So, there are a lot of online meetings [now]. And we can save some resources. Like, we [no longer] use transport to [go for meetings]. Most of our meetings were in [the capital town]. So, there is no longer shuttling and paying for transport. We only use data to access the meetings (Participant 7).

Similarly participant 8 from a Southern African country also shared how she is using digital skills to help cut costs in her work:

I've created so many workshops via, via zoom. This is an opportunity that I took. There's no need to go, have in person, like workshops and things in house. I mean, now people are saving, saving petrol money. We're also saving money on the food, the snacks, refreshments, we are saving money on travel, and the actual venue. So, I mean, this is the best opportunity that has come out [of the pandemic].

The above quotes clearly highlight how the digital skills that public and community librarians gained during the COVID-19 pandemic are positively helping the libraries to cut down on certain operational costs.

Library access to information technology (IT) equipment - “now all libraries have Internet”

We also identified that the COVID-19 pandemic presented African public and community libraries an opportunity to improve existing or acquire new IT equipment. Some of the libraries that hitherto did not have computers received some computers from their governments or from non-governmental institutions and even individuals. Some of those who already had computers, had their Internet connectivity or power supply improved. For instance, one of the librarians, a regional librarian from the southern province of a Western African country disclosed that “it was after COVID that the government brought in the Internet to the library...So, now all libraries have Internet.” (Participant 4). Similarly, one librarian from the second largest province of a Southern African country revealed that one of the libraries under her supervision was very lucky because they received “...30 laptops from an aspiring community leader” (Participant 2). While another librarian working in an internationally supported library from a Western African state added that:

One of the benefits and I know within the library we [had] two WiFi [routers]. But now we have about five WiFi [routers] along [...] the library premises, ground floor second floor, third floor and first floor we have all WiFi ...we [have also tried] to develop a kind of solar electricity system in the library for us to overcome the issue of power, electricity...we have five departments in the library and two departments are now powered with solar systems (Participant 1)

The above quotes show that due to the limited access to physical resources because of the pandemic, some governments and benevolent institutions or individuals went out of their way to procure or improve IT equipment and related infrastructure in public libraries in Africa so as to help them provide virtual information services to patrons.

Opportunity to initiate new library services- “had to think out of the box”

The librarians also mentioned that the pandemic presented them some opportunities to initiate new and innovative library services. For instance, a participant from a Northern African country revealed that due to the pandemic:

We had to think out of the box... so we ordered three mobile libraries [bookmobiles]. As a result of the outstanding work during the COVID, we are expanding. We are about to finish the procedure of buying extra three mobile libraries [bookmobiles] (Participant 5)

Some of the librarians revealed that they initiated other innovative, non-digital services such as providing meals for needy school kids to encourage them to attend classes when schools reopened as well as social cohesion talks to foster unity among families (see Bugre, Jowaisas and Young, 2023 for details).

Other libraries embraced the opportunity to be more innovative with digital tools. From an Eastern African country, we were told that “now, payment is by [name of a mobile money service]” (Participant 7) - for all public libraries to facilitate contactless payment for services like membership registrations, scanning and printing. The country’s national library authority was also in the process of launching a virtual library system to enable patrons to access library materials online. To this end, the library authority:

has also started a data center that will also keep information for other institutions. [Operations of the data center will help] so that in the future we will not depend [financially] on the government (Participant 7)

In a Western African country, the pandemic pushed its library authority to speed up the development and use of a mobile library application:

Actually, our executive director started putting something together. That is the app development way back before the COVID set in. So, when the COVID set in, there was like an added advantage for us to just build on it and let it stay. Because now we wanted it badly (Participant 6)

From a Southern African country, a participant revealed that the pandemic made them introduce virtual storytelling for kids via WhatsApp and YouTube. They also started to use WhatsApp to share scanned copies of reading materials to students. They mentioned that they relied “heavily on WhatsApp because...WhatsApp is the cheapest way of getting to people” (Participant 8)

The above testimonies demonstrate that the pandemic created several opportunities for African public and community libraries to introduce new and innovative library services. These services helped to meet various information needs of their communities during the COVID-19 pandemic. It also helped accelerate opportunities for expanding existing initiatives or services. While these discoveries were born out of the challenges during the pandemic, the opportunities and wisdom gained can be amplified using the Asset-Based Community Development (ABCD)

model to serve their communities now and in future crises as will be discussed in the next section.

We noticed that one messaging application, WhatsApp, was commonly used in a very innovative and proactive manner to facilitate information exchange among the librarians themselves and their patrons due to the absence of virtual service tools in many of these libraries. For instance, Participant 8 revealed to us that as the chair elect for the library association of a province in their country, they used WhatsApp to keep in touch with their members. Participant 8 depicted this vividly as follows:

I am the chair elect for our association. So, I formed a WhatsApp group with all the librarians in our province and we started hosting workshops. That was the cheapest means. So basically, I got people to come up with various topics. And the reason I did this was to keep people still updated and not getting brain dead sitting at home and doing absolutely nothing. It was wonderful because at a certain point we had 169 participants on that WhatsApp group. And we had topics such as, you know, like dealing with professional development... human centered management, just good topics to keep people updated and refreshed

The above illustrates how a simple and “cheap” messaging application, WhatsApp, was used to cope with the in-person constraints occasioned by the pandemic. In fact, all participants indicated using WhatsApp for either sharing resources with patrons or connecting with their colleagues to share ideas. The widespread use and applicability of WhatsApp in those African libraries during the pandemic presents an opportunity that libraries could use to expand existing information services now and in future times of crises.

Discussion

This paper looks at opportunities from the COVID-19 pandemic as described by African head librarians. Our findings suggest that the impact of the pandemic on African libraries was initially challenging but later spurred evolution of innovative services using mostly existing resources. The challenges from the COVID-19 pandemic also significantly pushed African librarians to learn new digital skills (e.g. teleconferencing and office application software). Similarly, the pandemic pushed some African governments and stakeholders to provide more information technology tools (e.g. donating computers and extending Wi-Fi capabilities) for African public

and community libraries to integrate virtual services into their operations. Again, some African libraries used existing mobile application platforms to deliver their services in innovative ways (e.g. introducing mobile money payments for paid library services, doing storytelling and sharing student materials via WhatsApp, and using WhatsApp for professional connections and development). Generally, the findings in this study mirror previous studies (African Library and Information Associations and Institutions, 2020; Bugre, Jowaisas and Young, 2023; Chigwada, 2021) but the novelty and significance of this study relate to how librarians can extend the COVID-19 pandemic opportunities by leveraging their existing resources and experiences as they did during the pandemic to serve the information needs of the users now and in future crises. In study, we focus on how librarians drew on their existing strengths and took advantage of opportunities from the pandemic to assist their community members. While the innovative services they initiated were born out of the challenges during the pandemic, the opportunities and wisdom gained can be amplified using the Asset-Based Community Development (ABCD) model to continue to serve and share information with their community members now and in future crises. In this discussion, we discuss four broad areas that public libraries should consider as they strive to take advantage of opportunities and to resolve the challenges they encountered during the pandemic. First, we discuss how librarians can leverage digital skills/resources acquired during the COVID-19 period to address mobile phone digital skills gaps since mobile phones are one of the most accessible digital tools in low-resourced environments. Participant 8 evoked the access to phones: "...this is a very poor community but many of the households here have phones. Phones are more important than food". Second, we discuss the need for improved/increased digital infrastructure as signaled by the pandemic but advocate a holistic approach. Third, we discuss in relation to the holistic approach, the need for digital security in the wake of increased cyber-attacks. Finally, we highlight the relation of the ABCD model to the experiences of our research participants and encourage librarians to do the same when faced with challenges. As illustrated above, the librarians initiated both digital and non-digital strategies during the pandemic, but we limit our discussion to the digital initiatives since the COVID-19 pandemic presented a strong case for virtual solutions. However, we argue that libraries should be mindful as they lobby for or roll out digital solutions.

Leverage acquired digital skills and mobile phones to address digital skills gaps among library staff and users

A major opportunity from the pandemic as shared by our participants was the opportunity for librarians to improve their digital skills and improve existing or acquire new digital tools. We believe this is an opportunity that librarians can leverage to further advance their own digital skills and build the digital skills of their communities. This need for digital skills in their communities was evoked by participant 3 when he said: “Many people in our communities have smartphones, but how to use it [them] profitably is still a big challenge”. But as expressed in other studies on the COVID-19 experiences of public librarians, many of them are not fluent in digital skills themselves (Shonhe, 2022). Nonetheless, public librarians are invited to educate the public on digital skills and digital misinformation (Kostagiolas and Katsani, 2021). We believe since the pandemic exposed the librarians to so many free online digital skills learning platforms, they can take advantage to further advance their skills to better support their community members. If both library staff and the broader community have a greater level of digital competencies then they will be better able to take advantage of technology-based tools now and during future crises. These skills will also help communities to navigate the everyday challenges of information technology such as misinformation. For instance, African public and community libraries can initiate mobile phone digital skills training services to build the resilience of their community members against misinformation. Misinformation –false, manipulated or inaccurate information– is also a global problem. Social media and mobile phones are largely the tools used to spread misinformation narratives (Wasserman, 2011). Misinformation drawn upon illiteracy tends to thrive (Joel and Camble, 2021) and could lead to worst political tensions and ethnic conflicts in Africa since democracy is still fragile across the continent (Mustapha, 2022) and illiteracy rates are high (Galan, 2025). Thus, public libraries are an important site of community intervention against misinformation (Chisita and Ngulube, 2022; Joel and Camble, 2021; Young et al., 2021). They can share audio or video tutorials via WhatsApp or other social media platforms as during the pandemic to reach adult populations who may not be able to attend in-person library services.

Improve digital infrastructure but adopt a holistic approach

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted a strong case for virtual operations to be integrated in public libraries as expressed by participant 2: “the lessons we learned, was that we really need to computerize yesterday... If you're, if you're closed for six months, and you're not giving any

service, really, are you necessary in a community?” This need is echoed by previous studies (Ayeni, Agbaje and Tipper, 2021; Chigwada, 2021; Bugre, Jowaisas and Young, 2023; Shonhe, 2022). But virtual capabilities are not a fix-all solution. As in the case of book mobiles (Participant 5) and other examples from literature (Roberts and Clarke, 2024), non-digital services can still be innovative and vital services to communities. Additionally, while funding for expanding IT became more available because of the pandemic in some cases, studies in similar contexts cite ongoing lack of policy or funds to support online services for public libraries (Dilrukshi, Illangarathne and Wanasinghe, 2021) and lack of ICT infrastructure (Shohone, 2022) which may be barriers to scaling pandemic innovations. Public and community libraries will have to continue to be inventive in analog ways. For example, if a library does not have Internet to host virtual storytelling for kids (Participant 8), it may be able to send a trusted staff member to escort children to the library for Storytime (Srirahayu, Harisanty and Anugrah, 2023) or offer their outdoor space for art or exercise activities (Lenstra and D' Arpa, 2022) in order to continue to benefit their patrons.

Thus, based on the lessons from the pandemic, we encourage library heads and policy makers to strive to go beyond simply trying to solve the library digital infrastructural challenges that were encountered during the pandemic and fortify their responses to meet current and future needs. They need to holistically build resilience for possible future crises that may be like the pandemic or others that could occur. One such holistic strategy could be looking at how libraries can continue to serve their patrons or communities using their current assets (Kretzmann and McKnight, 1993; McKnight and Russell, 2018; Russell and McKnight, 2022) in the event of possible crises. These assets may include their space, staff expertise, partnerships, community relationships, and others. Examining how libraries can depend on their current assets to meet the basic/essential needs of the community members in times of crises is more crucial than ever because the COVID-19 pandemic signaled that there could be times in our lives when, even if we have the means to acquire more resources, we cannot get anything elsewhere. We have to depend solely on what we have at hand. Participant 2 echoed this as follows: “It was just, it was not possible to acquire anything because you want to acquire this, but that factory or industry is closed because of COVID.” Libraries, therefore, need to take stock of what resources they have on hand that could be used in a crisis. The most important thing to note as advised by Campbell (2005) is to work with the patrons and not think for them.

Be mindful of cyber attacks as digital services are rolled out

Similarly, libraries should avoid just installing information systems and introducing virtual services without putting into place effective processes to minimize the effects of information technology challenges such as cyber-attacks. It is understandable that the goal at the peak of the pandemic was to keep people safe and to continue offering services as best possible. Thus, emphasis and recommendations for libraries without digital tools to acquire and install such tools to facilitate virtual services (Chigwada, 2021) was appropriate. But based on recent events – the massive Internet outage in Ghana, South Africa, Liberia, Ivory Coast and Burkina Faso in March, 2024 due to submarine cable breaks (Booty and Garzeawu, 2024); the ransomware attacks on libraries in locations such as the United Kingdom (The British Library, 2024), California (Fox-Sowell, 2024), and Seattle (Enis, 2024); and the global software outage that grounded planes, affected hospitals and disrupted critical public services (Satariano et al., 2024) – public and community libraries have to be mindful of the risks associated with the use of digital services. Apart from implementing techniques to avoid cyber-attacks, they should put in mechanisms through which they can serve their communities in the event of cyberattacks or technology breakdown. Bookmobiles and curated materials for hospital patients (Xin, 2022) are examples which show how libraries were able to meet their communities' needs at a specific moment in time without relying on technology. While it is tempting to see IT as the only route to innovation, these examples show the value of maintaining a variety of resources and the insight to use them creatively.

Always start with what is at your disposal

Finally, drawing from the interviews, many of the participants showed that depending on their current assets to meet essential needs during a crisis is possible. For instance, many of the libraries successfully provided valuable information services to their users notwithstanding their challenges by thinking outside the box: “Like sending information to people on WhatsApp” (Participant 3). This resonates with previous research that revealed that libraries used WhatsApp to send scanned portions of documents using mobile phone cameras to patrons such as students and researchers who needed them urgently when libraries were closed (African Library and Information Associations and Institutions, 2020; Bugre, Jowaisas and Young, 2023; Chigwada, 2021), and similar low cost platforms such as Facebook to disseminate information to library

users (Joel and Camble, 2021). While other platforms may be useful, participants reinforced that WhatsApp is most advantageous due to the low data requirements, ease of use, and popularity across Africa. The librarians were able to offer those services based on their existing assets such as their personal mobile phones, the library's information resources, their reputation in the community as a vital resource for students and researchers and their interpersonal relationship with community members which allowed those in need to reach out to them. All these are assets highlighted by the ABCD model (Kretzmann and McKnight, 1993; McKnight and Russell, 2018; Russell and McKnight, 2022) which libraries can explore and take advantage of to serve their community members now and in future crises. Nonetheless, they need to be mindful of copyright issues as they share information via social media (Smith, 2020).

Limitations and recommendations for further study

This study was limited to public librarians who could speak English. Although we tried to enhance inclusivity by recruiting participants who could speak English from non-English speaking African regions (For instance, from Egypt and Democratic Republic of Congo), further studies are needed to account for the experiences and initiatives of non-English speaking librarians during the COVID-19. This study is also limited by the sample size of 11 librarians. Although, to account for the limited sample size, we tried to recruit participants from different countries covering all the five sub-regions nonetheless, we recognize that this might not capture the full spectrum of the experiences and initiatives of public and community libraries across Africa, thus other studies can expand the sample size to remedy this limitation. Again, while virtual interviews are cost effective for the researcher and convenient in terms of privacy for the participants (Oliffe et al, 2021), there are also some limitations that pertain to the use of virtual interviews. For instance, some of our participants had unstable Internet connectivity. This affected the smooth flow of the conversation with them and made some of them sound inaudible, which affected the quality of the recordings. However, we mitigated this by sharing the transcripts with the participants to cross-check and fill in those gaps. In addition, while qualitative data provided rich insights, similar studies could be enhanced with quantitative data such as statistics on user engagement or the reach of virtual services.

Conclusion

This paper looked at the opportunities from the COVID-19 pandemic as shared by African head librarians using online semi-structured interviews and inductive thematic analysis. The study focused on opportunities identified by African public and community librarians and how those opportunities can be leveraged to initiate or expand information services to their communities drawing upon the ABCD model. We observed that some libraries successfully provided valuable information services to their users notwithstanding their challenges. Based on recent events such as the ransomware attacks, global software glitches and Internet interruptions, we argue that librarians should focus on holistic solutions as they think and plan for future possible crises like the COVID-19 pandemic and beyond.

However, these insights are limited to a cross-section of African public librarians that we interviewed. More research is needed to explore how libraries can use the Asset-Based Community Development (ABCD) model to serve their community members now and in possible future crises to shift the deficit mindset that low resourced libraries may have. This is very critical since one of the lessons that the COVID-19 pandemic taught us is the fact that there could be times in our lives that we cannot get anything elsewhere except to depend solely on what we have at hand. Therefore, library heads and policy makers should go beyond simply trying to solve library challenges that were encountered during the pandemic. They should explore both technological and non-technological solutions to current community issues using the ABCD model. The ABCD model provides insights in terms of how to adequately serve the needs of their communities by focusing on the library and its neighborhood's assets. Focusing on the institution's assets does not mean that institutions do not need additional or external support. But rather the ABCD model helps institutions to fully mobilize resources that they already have before looking outside to identify any additional external resources that may be required to meet their needs.

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